

DESIGN OF A MILLI-FLUIDIC CHAMBER FOR ASSESSING DRUG LOSS DUE TO BLOOD FLOW DURING DRUG-COATED BALLOON TRACKING

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Introduction

Drug-coated balloons (DCBs) are considered one of the primary endovascular treatments for peripheral artery disease. DCBs consist of an angioplasty balloon coated with a combination of an antiproliferative drug and an excipient [1]. DCBs are advanced over a guidewire to the target lesion and inflated transferring the drug to the stenotic vessel. However, during tracking, the blood flow, in combination with other biomechanical factors, affects the coating of the device, resulting in coating loss in the systemic circulation and creating potential distal embolization. [2]. To assess the impact of the blood flow to the coating loss during tracking a milli-fluidic chamber was developed and two different coating were examined.

Methods

For the design of the experimental set-up, a three-dimensional computational fluid dynamic (CFD) model was developed using ANSYS Fluent to assess the wall shear stress exerted on a commercial DCB within a superficial femoral artery (Fig. 1). Boundary conditions, incorporating velocity inlet and pressure outlet parameters, were implemented based on data from clinically relevant vessels obtained from the literature. To capture the range of Wall Shear Stress (WSS) values affecting the device during the clinical procedure, the DCB was simulated at various angles and positions. The maximum estimated WSS value was then utilized to determine, via analytical solution, the required flow rate and the dimensions implemented on the milli-fluidic chamber, aiming to replicate the in vivo environment. The milli-fluidic chamber was 3D printed and consisted of a rectangular shape, the dimensions of which were based on WSS numerical calculations. To validate the selected flow rate and dimensions, we developed a three-dimensional CFD model of the milli-fluidic chamber to estimate the WSS acting on the DCB specimen within the chamber. Two flat specimens with different coatings were glued to the center of the chamber. A syringe pump was used to apply the appropriate flow rate and a filter was used in the outlet to quantify the drug particles. Additionally, fluid samples were collected at specific intervals during the experiment and analyzed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) to assess coating loss over time.

Results

Preliminary HPLC analysis of the results revealed dependences of drug loss on different drug coated formulations. Size and number of particles are under

investigation for potential correlation with distal embolization.

Figure 1: 3D geometry of the idealized artery and commercial DCB b) velocity around the DCB in the center line position c) velocity around the DCB in angle position d) WSS on the DCB in centerline position e) WSS on the DCB in angle position

Figure 2: Milli-fluidic chamber.

Discussion

The experimental setup was designed to showcase the potential application of a milli-fluidic chamber in assessing the impact of blood flow on the coating loss in the systemic circulation. Quantification of particles in terms of number and size may characterize the potential severity of coating formulation regarding particle embolization in clinical condition. These setups could also be employed to simulate the impact of blood flow after deflation of the device and during retraction. The experimental configuration facilitates a thorough comprehension of different devices' performance, enabling for specific factors evaluations and refinements to ultimately enhance its clinical efficacy.

References

1. Bukka et al, J BioMed Matter., 13 (3), 2018
2. Shazly et al, J Bioeng Transl Med, 8(1), 2022.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956470.

